

COMBINATION OF A NOVEL ALL SKY IMAGER BASED APPROACH FOR HIGH-RESOLUTION SOLAR IRRADIANCE NOWCASTING WITH PERSISTENCE AND SATELLITE NOWCASTS FOR INCREASED ACCURACY

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ABSTRACT: Electricity grids with high PV-penetration benefit from the consideration of intra-minute and intra-hour variabilities via nowcasts (shortest-term forecasts). In this study we present approaches for blending all sky imager (ASI), persistence and satellite based nowcasts for increased nowcasting accuracy within the 15-minute interval. Our ASI method is a novel machine-learning (ML) based model, trained on spatially distributed irradiance measurements in Freiburg, Germany. These come from an irradiance measurement network of eight stations within a radius of ~10 km around the camera position, which we also use to evaluate our forecasting results.

Our ASI method exhibits a significantly lower root mean square error (RMSE) than the satellite-based method up to a lead time (LT) of 11 minutes ahead and a lower mean absolute error (MAE) throughout the entire interval. Using a LT dependent linear combination of the individual models RMSE improvement scores of 5 – 13% and MAE improvement scores of up to 6% (for $LT \geq 5 \text{ min}$) could be achieved over the respective optimal individual method. Further improvements in RMSE (up to 2%) and MAE (up to 7.5%) were achieved by using a Lasso model with 3rd degree polynomial features and including cloudiness, sun position and variability of clear-sky index as additional input parameters.

Keywords: All Sky-imager, irradiance nowcasting, machine learning, satellite data, model blending

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the fast extension of installed PV capacity worldwide, the generation characteristics within our electricity grids are in the process of undergoing a fundamental transformation: From a centralized electricity generation in relatively few major power plants towards a distributed generation on multiple plants of variable sizes. With the integration of large shares of distributed variable energy sources ([1] name of a share beyond 15% of annual energy production within the grid) significant changes in the operation of electrical grids become essential.

Synoptic and local weather patterns make solar irradiance a highly variable resource. Its forecasts hence make an important contribution to the integration of large shares of PV into the electricity grid [2].

On a local scale, solar irradiance can fluctuate with high amplitude on very short time scales due to passing clouds, also referred to as irradiance ramps. These ramps can result in sudden and heavy fluctuations in the power production of large PV-powerplants or distributed PV within quarters. This sets new challenges for all stakeholders including plant and grid operators.

Forecasts of solar irradiance based on numerical weather predictions (NWP) and the images of meteorological satellites have become established approaches to forecast solar irradiance days ahead and hours ahead respectively with a wide field of applications. However, neither of them can resolve single small-scale cloud structures and movements and therefore they are not suited for predicting irradiance ramps.

Nowcasts are high-resolution short-term irradiance forecasts for the immediate future [2], herein up to 15 minutes ahead. Based on these, fine-grained control applications can be performed to handle short-term fluctuations of PV-power in a beneficial way for the grid and other stakeholders involved. The control of heat pumps and cooling systems [3], as well as management of large battery storages, offgrid PV-Diesel systems and the short-term electricity market (up to 5 minutes ahead, [2]) are just a few examples of applications that can profit from accurate nowcasting.

In this study we investigate approaches of blending nowcasts of a novel all sky imager (ASI) model, persistence and satellite-based nowcasts.

Nowcasts are computed for a dataset spanning over one entire year and evaluated against measurements from our irradiance measuring network. This network includes eight measuring stations within a radius of ~10 km around the camera position.

Our first nowcasting approach is a persistence model, assuming persistence of clear-sky index at the respective position. The clear-sky index k_{clear}^* is defined as the ratio between current global horizontal irradiation (GHI) and GHI under clear-sky conditions [2]. Secondly, we use a satellite-based (SAT) approach [4] based on the well-established Heliosat method [5]. Using images of Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) forecasts with a temporal resolution of 15 minutes up to a few hours ahead can be computed. Within this study we only use the first LT step (15 minutes ahead), which is linearly interpolated to create nowcasts that match the 1-minute resolution of the ASI.

With its capability to predict short-term irradiance variability an ASI model is the centerpiece of our blending experiments. Here we use the novel ASI model (initially) reported in [6]. ASIs capture images of the sky in regular intervals to track clouds and their motion. Future cloud situations are predicted by extrapolating these movements into the future. Nowcasts are computed by modelling radiative effects of clouds either by applying statistical models to (short-term) historic irradiance measurements or, as done here, using machine learning (ML) methods, and applying the information to predicted cloud situations. To create areal forecasts clouds must be geolocated either using the cloud base height (CBH) from ceilometer measurements or multiple ASIs with overlapping fields of view to perform stereo photography. Subsequently, cloud shadows are projected onto their real-world positions on the ground exploiting cloud and sun position. Thereby spatial coverage and forecasting horizon can be extended by using multiple or even networks of ASIs [7]. Nevertheless many ASI methods reported of only generate

Figure 1: (a) Map of our irradiance measuring network. The blue circle has a radius of 10 km, the ASI is located in the center (marked red). Stations with a star are equipped with both MS80 and ML01 pyranometers, the remaining stations only with ML01 pyranometers; (b) Measurement station with EKO MS80, ML01 pyranometers and tilted reference cells. Within this work we only use EKO MS80 and ML01.

point nowcasts (usually for the camera position) not providing any spatial resolution [8–10].

Blending of different forecasting models is a common approach that reduces forecasting errors compared to the respective individual methods [11–13]. Model blending approaches within the short-term interval, however, have so far been hardly investigated.

As a baseline for our hybrid model, we use a lead time (LT) dependent linear combination of the three individual methods (see also [6]). The weights are determined via a linear regression on each LT using the three respective nowcasts as input and the corresponding measurement as target value. Here, in addition we investigate more sophisticated blending approaches beyond linear models, including additional input features such as cloudiness and variability of clear-sky index are investigated.

2 DATASET

We use GHI measurements from a network of eight measuring stations within Freiburg to train our ASI- and hybrid models and to evaluate forecasting results. These measuring stations are located within a radius of approximately 10 km around the camera position (Figure 1 (a)). An off-the-shelf surveillance camera (Vivotek FE9381) located in the center of the map is used as ASI, recording images every 10 s. Our measuring setup is shown in Figure 1 (b). Four of the stations (tagged with a star) are equipped with a ventilated thermal pyranometer (EKO MS-80) which has a particularly low response time (< 0.5 s) and a silicon pyranometer (EKO ML-01). The remaining stations are equipped with silicon pyranometers only. All sensors record instantaneous GHI with second resolution. Wherever they are available, measurements from the thermal pyranometers are used, as they exhibit lower uncertainties [14, 15].

Moreover, our ASI-method uses ceilometer measurements of cloud base height (CBH) from a nearby ceilometer (distance to ASI $d_{ASI} \approx 1$ km) operated by the German weather service Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD).

All irradiance measurements used within this work undergo an extensive quality control (QC) procedure [16] to ensure data quality. The scope of our QC method is to

identify flawed measurements and, if possible, correct or otherwise discard them.

The measuring station at the position of the sky imager is equipped with a sun tracker from EKO (STR-22G) measuring DNI with a pyrhelimeter (MS-56) and diffuse horizontal irradiance DHI with a pyranometer shaded by a shadow ball (MS-802F). This sophisticated setup provides the highest measurement quality within the measuring network and serves as reference within our QC.

2.1 Training and test data

Our measuring campaign started in February 2018 and is running ever since. Within this study one entire year from (including) Mai 2021 to April 2022 was selected. Using one year of data aims at giving a balanced representation of the seasonal course of meteorological conditions on our testing site.

The dataset split for the ASI and the hybrid model is illustrated in Table 1. In total the dataset was split twice: For training of the ASI irradiance retrieval method (compare section 3.1) all odd days of the year have been used. ASI, SAT and persistence nowcasts were computed in the remaining even days of the year (in the following nowcasting-dataset). Subsequently the nowcasting-dataset was split to create a training and test dataset for our hybrid method. As four entire days are missing in our nowcasting-dataset we use every second day *available* to split it into evenly sized train and test datasets.

Both, measurements and nowcasts used in this work are instantaneous values. Nowcasts are computed throughout the entire previously described periods for sun zenith angles of $\leq 80^\circ$ and with a temporal resolution of 1 minute. In principle, our ASI method can provide finer resolutions (down to 10 s) but as comparison to and blending with SAT nowcasts is the scope of this work minute resolution was chosen here. Nowcasts of all methods are computed with a base-time (starting time of each nowcast run) frequency of 15 minutes due to the update frequency of satellite images.

Nowcast horizon is set to 15 minutes ahead. The maximum possible nowcasting horizon of our ASI method depends on the prevailing cloud conditions. It can be longer or less than the intended 15 minutes ahead. Truncated nowcast

runs with a maximum LT of less than 15 minutes are considered in the evaluation. For these instances SAT and persistence nowcasts are filtered to the same maximum LT to ensure best possible comparability among our methods.

Table 1: Illustration of train test split of the ASI and hybrid model training. Splitting scheme continues after the depicted period throughout the entire dataset.

		Day of dataset								
Split		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	...
1										
2										

■ ASI Training ■ Individual methods Nowcast
■ Hybrid Training ■ Hybrid Nowcast

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 ASI nowcasting

Our ASI nowcasting method uses camera images, local irradiance measurements at the position of the camera and CBH measurements to generate spatially and temporally highly resolved (1 minute and $\approx 2 - 10$ m, depending on CBH) areal nowcasts of GHI. Our ASI nowcasting chain is illustrated in Figure 2. It builds on the ASI method described in [17] and includes the following steps:

- Recording of all sky image
- Rectification to compensate fisheye distortion
- Computation of clear-sky index images using ML-method
- Identifying cloud movements by computing optical flow from two consecutive rectified ASI images
- Prediction of future clear-sky index images by applying the computed optical flow to (c)
- Forecast of GHI maps by projecting clear-sky indices onto their real-world position and scaling them with computed clear-sky irradiation.

In [6] we extend the original approach from point to areal nowcasting by geolocating clouds and projecting their shadows onto real-world positions. Instead of the statistical irradiance retrieval from recent GHI histograms, an adapted version of the ML method from [16] is used to assign distinct GHI levels to each image pixel (hereinafter irradiance algorithm). The remaining steps (a, b, d) and algorithms are equivalent to the original approach. The single steps are described in [6] in more detail.

3.2 Satellite based nowcasts

Our satellite based nowcasting method (SAT-method) is based on [4] and uses data from the geostationary MSG satellite. We use the well-established Heliosat method, in a version based on [5] to infer irradiance. This method mainly exploits the broadband visible channel to determine the irradiance transfer through clouds. At that, the pixel intensity is a crucial parameter that serves as a measure for the backscattering and transmission within the clouds. The brighter a pixel appears, the stronger the backscattering ensuing lower irradiance levels on the ground. To detect and forecast cloud movement, we use block matching on two consecutive satellite images.

With this approach forecasts up to several hours ahead can be computed. The spatial resolution of the forecasts is 1 km x 1 km at sub-satellite point and approximately 1.2 km,

Figure 2: Overview ASI nowcasting method. (a) recording of ASI image, (b) image undistortion, (c) computation of clear-sky index image, (d) computation of optical flow, (e) forecasting clear-sky index image, (f) forecasting irradiance map. Note, that from step (e) to (f) the clear-sky image is mirrored along the y-axis resulting from the projection.

x 2.2 km in the region of Freiburg. The temporal resolution is determined by the 15-minute time lapse between two consecutive satellite images. To reach the required 1-minute resolution, forecasted clear-sky indices are linearly interpolated (upsampling).

3.3 Persistence

Persistence nowcasts assume persistence of prevailing conditions. Taking into account diurnal variations of irradiance, i.e. assuming persistence of clear-sky index, nowcasted GHI_{per} at a given time t is given by [2]:

$$GHI_{per}(t) = GHI_{clear}(t) \cdot k^*(t_0) \quad (1)$$

Thereby $k^*(t_0)$ denotes the clear-sky index at the current moment. In this work we use persistence based on the clear-sky index derived from measurements for each of the stations of the network. This is consistent with the common persistence definition used in most publications. That way persistence nowcasts have the same quality for each measuring station.

In an operational scenario real-time irradiance measurements are not necessarily available at each position of interest. In that case persistence of clear-sky index of the closest irradiance measurement can be applied instead.

3.4 Model blending

Starting point of our model blending experiments is a LT-dependent linear combination of the individual nowcasts, in the following referred to as stepwise linear hybrid model. The hybrid nowcast from this basic model therefore is the weighted sum of the individual nowcasts, whereas the weights of each method vary with LT.

To derive the coefficients, data from our hybrid training dataset is binned by LT-step. Separate regressions are performed on each LT-step, resulting in a separate set of coefficients for each instance.

3.4.1 Advanced model blending

After establishing a basic reference model, we investigate more elaborate ML-methods and additional input features to further enhance our results.

Besides LT, the performance of our individual models might depend on other parameters. These dependencies are not considered in our baseline approach. Here, cloudiness, variability of clear-sky index within the past 15 minutes and cosine of sun zenith angle are added as additional input features. Moreover, LT is used as an input feature instead of separate models for each LT. To reflect the presumably non-linear relations between model in- and output more sophisticated (non-linear) methods are investigated. We use the same set of input features in all our advanced blending approaches. These are listed in Table 2. Cloudiness is computed as the fraction of cloud-classified pixels in undistorted ASI images. Thereto, we use the cloud classification algorithm from [17]. Variability of clear-sky index is computed according to [18].

Six methods were preselected and hyperparameter optimized. Our six candidates include scikit-learn's [19] python implementations of gradient boosting regression (GBR), extremely randomized trees regression (Extra Trees) and a random forest regressor (Random Forest) with default parameters each. Moreover, k-nearest neighbors regression (kNN) with distance weights and 50 neighbors, and a Lasso (Lasso) model with 3rd degree polynomial features and $\alpha = 0.5$ (scikit-learn) and a neuronal network (NN) with two hidden dense layers of 200 nodes each (tensorflow) are deployed.

Table 2: List of input features for our advanced combinations

Name	Description
Individual Nowcasts	ASI, SAT and Persistence nowcasts
Nowcasting LT	LT step in minutes
Cloudiness	Fraction of cloud classified pixels over number of valid pixels in undistorted image
$\cos(\theta_{sun})$	Cosine of sun zenith angle at ASI position
Variability k^*	Variability of clear-sky index [18] within the past 15 minutes

3.5 Error metrics

The error between an observation x_i and the corresponding prediction y_i is given by:

$$\epsilon_i = y_i - x_i \quad (2)$$

To compare model performances, we consider the root mean squared error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) and their normalized counterparts ($RMSE_{rel}$ and MAE_{rel}):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n \epsilon_i^2} \quad (3)$$

$$RMSE_{rel} = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n |\epsilon_i| \quad (5)$$

$$MAE_{rel} = \frac{MAE}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100\% \quad (6)$$

In the context of forecasting the skill evaluates the forecast performance compared to a trivial reference method with regard to a certain error metric (e.g. RMSE) [2]. It is calculated from the forecast score S_{fc} in the respective metric, the score of the reference forecast S_{ref} and the score of a perfect forecast S_{perf} (e.g. $S_{perf, RMSE} = 0$):

$$Skill = \frac{S_{ref} - S_{fc}}{S_{ref} - S_{perf}} \quad (7)$$

The skill is positive if the respective score shows an improvement compared to the reference method, zero if its equivalent and negative if it performs worse. It can reach a maximum value of 1 implying a perfect Score ($S_{fc} = S_{perf}$). When compared to a non-trivial method as reference this metric is referred to as improvement score. Here, we evaluate the RMSE skill of our methods in comparison to persistence and the improvement of the hybrid model compared to the single models with respect to RMSE and MAE.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Individual nowcasts and linear blending

Nowcasting results of our individual methods and hybrid model evaluated on all measuring stations are shown in Figure 2. Regarding the three individual methods the persistence nowcast performs best in terms of RMSE for lead times (LTs) up to 2 min. (Figure 3 (a)). For $LT = 0$ the persistence nowcast is the measured value at this exact instance. Starting at zero its RMSE quickly rises with LT. Subsequently the ASI takes over until $LT = 11 min$ after which the satellite gains a slight edge compared to the ASI. Generally forecasting performances of all types of models decrease with increasing LTs. Opposed to that, a decline of RMSE and MAE with increasing LTs can be observed in the satellite curve (Figure 3 (a) and (b)). As outlined in section 2.1, data is filtered to situations where nowcasts of all methods are available. ASI nowcasts tend to drop out over LT in situations with high cloud velocities and thereby high variability. This causes a decline in mean variability over LT in the filtered dataset. On the remaining more stable situations lower error metrics are observed for all methods, causing a decline in RMSE and MAE for the SAT nowcasts.

When performing the same evaluation but considering complete nowcast runs only an increase of RMSE and MAE over LT could be observed for all methods (not shown). This way the dataset (variability-)composition remains unaltered over LT.

Figure 3: Nowcasting results of the four different methods on the test dataset (a) relative RMSE, (b) relative MAE, (c) Distribution of clear-sky indices of nowcast and measurement all LT combined and (d) contributions of each method to the stepwise linear hybrid model over LT.

All in all, the performances of the three methods match the respective temporal scale they are designed for and illustrate the sense of purpose of blending different methods with varying contributions over LT.

Regarding relative MAE (Figure 3 (b)), our persistence method shows the best individual performance until $LT = 9 \text{ min}$. After that, our ASI method takes over for the rest of the nowcasting interval. The SAT method shows the highest relative MAE for all LT. RMSE penalizes larger errors and outliers more than MAE, which tends to promote smoother nowcasts such as the SAT nowcast. Different error distributions of our models result in different courses of MAE and RMSE curves. Persistence reflects the full range of GHI values observed, resulting in a higher number of outliers which is penalized by RMSE. Clear-sky index distributions of ASI, SAT and our stepwise linear hybrid model for all LTs combined are shown in Figure 3 (c). The distribution of our persistence nowcasts is inherently (almost perfectly) equivalent to the measured distribution and is therefore left out here. Measurements exhibit a notable spread around $k^* = 1$. This can be caused by variations in turbidity as well as reflections on cloud bottom sides that cause irradiance levels beyond clear-sky conditions. These aspects are insufficiently reflected within our nowcasting methods and clear-sky model, resulting in a sharp peak at $k^* = 1$. Values beyond that point are underrepresented. This underrepresentation is more significant for the SAT than for the ASI method. By design our SAT-method does not

predict $k^* > 1.2$. Its initial 15-minute values are linearly interpolated to a 1-minute resolution, such that all instances except $LT = 0$ and $LT = 15 \text{ Min}$ are interpolated values (compare section 3.2). This creates a smooth nowcast with an over proportional share of values in the intermediate range ($\approx 0.6 - 0.9$) and an underrepresentation for $k^* > 1$ correspondingly. The k^* -distribution of our ASI-nowcasts is influenced by the RMSE optimized training procedure. To avoid large errors the ASI method favors intermediate values over extreme values likewise causing an overrepresentation in the intermediate range. This overrepresentation is however less pronounced than for the SAT method. Besides lower MAE and RMSE (within certain LT intervals) an advantage of the ASI over the SAT-method is the possibility to have higher update frequencies than the 15 minutes prescribed by the satellite.

Our stepwise linear hybrid model exhibits the lowest RMSE compared to any of the individual models over the entire interval. Regarding MAE it performs best for $LT \geq 5 \text{ min}$. The contribution of each method as a function of LT is depicted in Figure 3 (d). The stepwise linear method benefits from all three nowcasting methods, exploiting their varying contributions throughout the short-term interval. As expected, these contributions are correlated to the model's performances: The lower the RMSE (Figure 3 (a)) the higher the corresponding models' contribution. For very short LT ($\leq 3 \text{ min}$) the persistence nowcast makes by far the largest contribution, which quickly

Figure 4: MAE (a) and RMSE (b) improvement scores of our advanced compared to our basic stepwise linear hybrid model.

decreases throughout the 15-minute time window. The contribution of ASI quickly increases within the first minutes. From $LT \approx 3 \text{ min}$ onwards it is the dominant method within the hybrid nowcast. By LT dependent linear combination of our individual nowcasting results an RMSE improvement score of 5 – 13% compared to the respective optimal individual method was achieved. A positive MAE improvement score of up to 6% can be achieved for $LT \geq 5 \text{ min}$. Our individual methods differ in their error distributions and therefore exhibit different courses of RMSE and MAE curves (Figure 3 (a) and (b)). Hence our RMSE optimized stepwise linear model does not minimize MAE, resulting in a lower MAE than RMSE improvement score. A much more detailed investigation of model performance including a variability analysis is given in [6].

4.2 Advanced model blending

RMSE and MAE improvement scores of our advanced blending approaches with our stepwise linear hybrid model as reference are depicted in Figure 4 (a) and (b).

Positive RMSE improvement score is shown by our Lasso method throughout the entire interval and by the GBR within $3 \text{ min} \leq LT \leq 6 \text{ min}$. Other than that, RMSE improvement scores are all negative. Our Lasso method exhibits the highest positive values with $\approx 0 - 2\%$.

Higher improvements can be observed regarding MAE. For $LT \leq 9 \text{ min}$ our NN shows the highest improvement scores of up to $\approx 8\%$ which quickly declines to 0 outside this interval. Our Lasso approach exhibits positive MAE improvement scores throughout the entire interval ranging from $\approx 4 - 7.5\%$. Within certain LT intervals positive MAE improvement score is shown by all remaining methods except Random Forest.

As mentioned, nowcasting performance was enhanced significantly less in terms of MAE with our stepwise linear blending approach compared to the individual methods (Figure 4 (b)) leaving higher potential for improvement regarding this metric.

With our advanced blending models, we could achieve a significant, yet somewhat limited performance improvements compared to our linear hybrid model. One cause for that limitation might be, that the selected additional parameters in the advanced approach are not separating the performances of the individual models well. As a result the hybrid model cannot learn virtues of the individual models under specific conditions resulting in only slight improvements. Nowcasting performance can

however only be improved to a certain degree with this blending approach as our individual nowcasts themselves have limited accuracy.

We found that higher complexity models such as our neuronal network and others like transformers (in preliminary experiments) tend to perform worse than simpler models. Thereby adding or replacing further additional features likewise led to performance deterioration, probably due to overfitting. All in all, we therefore conjecture that there is limited potential for further improvement with this approach.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this work a novel ASI method for high resolution areal nowcasting was benchmarked against persistence and SAT nowcasts with LTs up to 15 min. To match the ASI resolution, linear interpolation was applied to the SAT nowcasts. Different approaches were investigated to blend nowcasts of these three individual methods. Areal nowcasts were computed every 15 min with a temporal resolution of 1 min for LTs up to 15 min ahead on every fourth day throughout one entire year. The validation was performed with a network of eight measuring stations in the city region of Freiburg, within a radius of $\approx 10 \text{ km}$ around the ASI position.

Regarding our three individual methods persistence exhibits the lowest RMSE for $LT \leq 2 \text{ min}$ and lowest MAE for $LT \leq 9 \text{ min}$. The SAT method shows the lowest RMSE from all individual methods towards the end of the interval ($LT \geq 12 \text{ min}$) and highest MAE throughout all LT. It produces very smooth nowcasts on a minute timescale due to its linear interpolation, which results in a better performance regarding RMSE than MAE.

Within $2 \text{ min} < LT < 12 \text{ min}$ our novel ASI method exhibits the lowest RMSE and for $LT \geq 10 \text{ min}$ the lowest MAE of the individual methods. Clear-sky index distributions indicate that our ASI nowcasts exhibit some smoothing but significantly less pronounced as the SAT method. Compared to SAT nowcasts ASI nowcasts have the additional advantage of a higher updating frequency, which wasn't examined in detail in this work. One way to increase the forecasting horizon and spatial coverage of ASIs is the use of multiple ASIs with adjacent fields of view. Another approach is to use a hybrid model that fills up gaps in ASI nowcasts with nowcasts from other methods. This way individual methods, designed for

different spatio-temporal scales, can be used to complement each other.

In addition to the lead time dependent linear blending several more advanced approaches were tested and compared. Our stepwise linear hybrid model outperforms the three individual methods on any LT by an RMSE improvement score of 5% – 13% compared to the respective optimal method. A positive MAE improvement score of up to 6% can be achieved for $LT \geq 5 \text{ min}$ (see also [6]). By blending our nowcasts with a Lasso model with cloudiness, sun position and variability as additional inputs and 3rd degree polynomial features we could further improve our stepwise linear approach by an RMSE improvement score of $\approx 1\%$. More remarkable is the MAE improvement score of $\approx 4 - 7.5\%$ for $LT \geq 2 \text{ min}$. More sophisticated models like transformers with further input information performed worse in preliminary experiments. Based on these experiments, we presume that the potential of the model blending approach is mostly tapped with the proposed Lasso model and there is little room for further improvement.

However, we see great potential in investigating novel image-based ML-based methods for predicting future cloud situations. In the field of short-term precipitation nowcasting novel methods based on convolutional neuronal networks have led to great improvements and outperformed state-of-the-art methods within recent years [20, 21].

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Parts of this research were funded by the European Union as part of the project SERENDI-PV. Special thanks go out to the German Federal Environmental Foundation (DBU) for supporting this work with a fellowship.

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